

N. A. Gumar, A. A. Satmurzaev

Temporary Storage Warehousing during Customs Operations in the Asia-Pacific Region

KEYWORDS

multimodal transportation,
transport and logistics hub,
customs operations,
customs control,
temporary storage warehouse,
container,
trade

ABSTRACT

Introduction. The organization of temporary storage warehousing in the Asia-Pacific region enhances logistical efficiency, ensures supply chain flexibility, facilitates tax savings, and supports the secure storage of sensitive goods. Collectively, this contributes to the development of regional trade and the strengthening of logistical infrastructure.

The research is aimed at examining the functionality of modern temporary storage warehouses and the specifics of temporary storage warehousing during customs operations in the Asia-Pacific region.

Materials and Methods. The research materials included articles from leading scientific journals, proceedings of international conferences, and data from analytical organizations. The research methods encompassed analysis of existing literature and regulatory documents, review of industry reports and statistical data, as well as the application of descriptive statistics to assess current trends.

Results. The analysis of the temporary storage warehousing market specifics in the Asia-Pacific region indicates its dynamic growth. According to Mordor Intelligence, the market size for self-storage was estimated at 32.88 million square feet by 2025, with an expected increase to 50.35 million square feet by 2031, assuming an average annual growth rate of 7.36%. The region is characterized by a mix of developed and developing economies, fostering a diversity of market strategies and infrastructure solutions. In countries such as Singapore and Hong Kong, digital customs clearance systems and integrated port-warehouse ecosystems are successfully implemented, enhancing logistical efficiency. In Southeast Asian countries, logistics capacities are expanding, and inventory management models are being adopted to ensure more effective handling of seasonal peaks.

Conclusion. The obtained data confirm that the development of the self-storage warehousing market in the Asia-Pacific region depends on factors such as urbanization, population growth, and increasing middle-class income. Megacities like Shanghai, Tokyo, and Mumbai face shortages of residential space and high-density development, necessitating new storage formats. The growth of e-commerce also stimulates demand for flexible logistics solutions. Overall, such warehouse complexes, functioning as micro-hubs, are cost-effective and scalable, meeting modern market requirements and contributing to the region's enhanced competitiveness.

FOR CITATION

Received: Sep 14, 2025
Accepted: Dec 11, 2025
Published: Mar 1, 2026

Gumar, N. A., & Satmurzaev, A. A. (2026). Temporary Storage Warehousing during Customs Operations in the Asia-Pacific Region. *Economic Consultant*, (1), 4–23. <https://doi.org/10.46224/ecoc.2026.1.1>

This is an open access article distributed under a Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike International License (CC-BY-SA 4.0) that allows others to share the work with an acknowledgement of the work's authorship and initial publication in this journal

INTRODUCTION

The organization of temporary storage warehousing within the framework of customs operations in the Asia-Pacific region is gaining strategic relevance due to a number of key factors. Firstly, it helps reduce time expenditures and enhance the efficiency of logistics processes by enabling accelerated customs clearance and minimizing delays in the cross-border movement of goods. Secondly, the implementation of such warehousing solutions provides flexibility and adaptability to the internal supply chain, which is particularly important given the high dynamism of cargo flow volumes, seasonal fluctuations, and demand volatility in the region, especially in Southeast Asian countries. Furthermore, the use of customs warehouses allows for the deferral of customs duties and tax payments, thereby improving the financial liquidity of participants in foreign economic activity and optimizing tax liabilities. In the context of storing particularly sensitive goods, such as pharmaceuticals and perishable products, customs warehouses ensure compliance with preservation conditions and prevent product spoilage, which enhances the safety level of logistics operations. Finally, the development of temporary storage infrastructure contributes to the expansion of regional trade and the formation of multimodal logistics hubs, stimulating both intra-regional and extra-regional trade. Overall, the organization of temporary storage is a significant factor in increasing the competitiveness and efficiency of logistics systems in the Asia-Pacific region.

Amid rising production costs and shifts in trade policy, many manufacturers are diversifying their supply chains. A significant number of companies are relocating procurement sources and production capacities to Asia to maintain economic efficiency and reduce excessive dependence on any single country. This situation can be mitigated through the use of customs warehouses, which function as duty-free trade zones.

A customs warehouse is a secured storage facility recognized by customs authorities, intended for storing goods imported from outside other countries. Its use allows for the deferral of customs duties and taxes, such as VAT, until the actual release of goods into the customs territory or their re-export.

A customs warehouse is a secure location for storing goods that are outside the customs regime for a specified period. Goods placed in such a warehouse remain under customs control but are exempt from the payment of import duties, VAT, and other taxes during the storage period [1]. Taxes and duties become

payable only at the moment of the goods' release into the customs territory – upon their distribution within the EU, re-export, or other permitted uses, such as destruction or inward processing.

Customs warehouses represent an effective tool for reducing the tax burden, increasing inventory management flexibility, and accelerating logistics processes for goods imported from outside other countries. Their application allows companies to optimize financial flows, improve operational efficiency, and maintain strategic stocks near key markets. Similar principles apply to excise warehouses under specific regulations, expanding optimization opportunities for goods subject to excise taxation.

For manufacturers of electronics and high-tech components, the use of customs warehouses in the Asian region is becoming a strategic tool for optimizing tax liabilities and enhancing the efficiency of utilizing the region's growing production capacities.

The research is aimed at examining the functionality of modern temporary storage warehouses and the specifics of temporary storage warehousing during customs operations in the Asia-Pacific region.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The research materials consisted of scientific articles from authoritative peer-reviewed journals (including SN Applied Sciences; Electronic Commerce Research; Journal of Marine Science and Technology; Humanities and Social Sciences Communications; Operations Management Research; Advances in Science, Technology & Innovation; Journal of Transportation Security; Journal of Shanghai Jiaotong University; Smart Innovation, Systems and Technologies; International Economics and Economic Policy), proceedings of international conferences (such as Lecture Notes in Civil Engineering; SADASC 2022: Communications in Computer and Information Science; Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems; Lecture Notes in Mechanical Engineering; Lecture Notes in Electrical Engineering; Lecture Notes in Intelligent Transportation and Infrastructure; ISPC 2023: Springer Proceedings in Business and Economics), and data from analytical organizations (Persistence Market Research, Future Market Insights, Mordor Intelligence, Grand View Research, among others).

The research methods employed included analysis of existing literature and regulatory documents; review of industry reports and statistical data to assess current trends; descriptive statistics.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Logistics in the organization of temporary storage warehousing involves the effective planning of placement, movement, and inventory accounting of goods to minimize time and costs. Optimization methods include the use of modern information systems, process automation, modeling, and analytical tools (e.g., linear programming, flow simulation) to determine optimal storage volumes, routes, and timelines, as well as the implementation of tracking and inventory management technologies to enhance efficiency and reduce costs.

F. Hoyano and A. Ishigaki note that previous research insufficiently accounted for the location of temporary storage facilities used for batch picking of category-based products, as well as the capacity of pickers. The authors refine the method for calculating the number of circular trips that must be considered when classifying picking schemes and propose a method for determining efficient picking schemes using dynamic programming [2].

P. W. Albert et al. provide a literature review on distribution planning methods and warehouse layout design that could be suitable for solving practical industry problems, with a focus on heterogeneous and non-standard spare parts [3].

A. K. Sinha and P. Muralidhar identify challenges at various levels of warehouse operations. The authors then define and apply appropriate lean manufacturing tools and methods to address these issues. This leads to a reduction in waste, an increase in productivity, and an improvement in the efficiency of warehouse operations [4].

X. Hu and Y. F. Chuang optimize e-commerce warehouse layout and enhance sorting efficiency. A genetic algorithm is used to solve the nonlinear programming model, enabling a scientifically grounded e-commerce warehouse layout plan. After re-planning, cargo handling costs can be significantly reduced through optimization, with the optimization rate of the objective function reaching 39.25% [5].

Scholars focus on determining warehouse dimensions and optimizing their areas, which is primarily aimed at standardizing and optimizing warehouse space assessment. Researchers propose a branch-and-cut algorithm, supported by specific storage strategies, highlighting the efficiency of operations research as a problem-solving tool [6].

W. K. Hsu et al. point out that container terminals (CTs) within a single port are often located in multiple sites, which can lead to a range of operational, economic, and environmental drawbacks related to the allocation of resources for port operations.

The researchers demonstrate that the five most important criteria regarding CT relocation policy include investment attraction incentives (10.89%), intra-port cooperation-competition (10.85%), container throughput growth rate (8.55%), the customs clearance system (8.10%), and the tax rate (6.94%) [7].

Scholars examine the core functions of cargo operations, including handling, storage, sorting, and customs procedures, while also highlighting the unique challenges European airports face in managing large volumes of air freight, ensuring security, and complying with regulatory standards. The researchers propose recommendations for improving the performance of cargo terminals, such as implementing automation, advanced tracking technologies, and sustainable practices aimed at reducing environmental impact [8].

Y. Zhao et al. defined a sampling method for a comprehensive solution that meets stakeholder interests in cross-border e-commerce from the perspectives of accuracy, timeliness, and sustainability. The authors proposed a toolkit to enhance customs clearance efficiency by applying theoretical sampling analysis methods to problems arising during customs operations [9].

N. Bandaranayake et al. developed a reference model for analyzing and improving processes specific to Cross-Border Logistics (CBL) systems. The effectiveness of the reference model was demonstrated using two targeted case studies [10].

Automation methods in organizing temporary storage warehousing include the implementation of Warehouse Management Systems (WMS), the use of electronic and mobile platforms for inventory accounting and tracking, automated loading/unloading systems, RFID and barcoding for rapid cargo identification and accounting, as well as integration with ERP systems to optimize logistics processes.

The widespread adoption of information and digital technologies in the control activities of customs authorities has become a natural outcome of the development of international and domestic approaches to improving customs services and enhancing the efficiency of foreign economic activity overall. In this context, a scientific understanding of the current state of digitalization in customs authorities' activities and identifying prospects for the further development of information and digital technologies in the context of improving control activities acquires particular importance [11].

S. Mamyrova et al. assess the role of digital technologies in ensuring secure international transportation and customs supervision. Furthermore, a theoretical evaluation of the effectiveness and feasibility of implementing a "single window"

system in these countries was conducted, which significantly improves coordination between national customs services (as WTO members), foreign trade organizations, customs authorities, and government bodies responsible for foreign economic activity and licensing [12].

B. Valetskyi et al. conducted an analysis of warehouse system parameters and developed a computer program for their automated calculation. The "Warehouse Calculator" software creates a sketch of a warehouse with pallet racking according to specified input and output parameters. The program's algorithm calculates the warehouse area, its geometric dimensions (length, width, and height), taking into account the values and dimensions entered by the user [13].

Y. Pan et al. propose a project for an intelligent optimized warehouse operation planning management system using multiple AGVs. Based on research into multi-task planning, the system develops assumptions and simulations for warehouse layout, vehicle operation rules, etc. [14].

Y. Chen and Z. Jiang, aiming to solve the problem of efficiency mismatch between stacker cranes and Automated Guided Vehicles (AGVs), as well as the lack of effective AGV operation planning, developed a multi-AGV task planning model based on a daily planning cycle and minimizing vehicle energy consumption. According to the authors, the algorithm is capable of finding optimal planning schemes, and the effectiveness of a penalty strategy for inter-vehicle conflicts is analyzed [15].

G. Prokudin et al., to implement an analytical model of a customs terminal's operation in managing variable cargo modules, developed a Customs Terminal Queuing Network Analysis System (SACTMSN) in the Excel environment. Calculations of the cargo customs terminal's operation mode as a queuing system using real-world examples showed pathways for optimizing terminal operations [16].

R. Seturidze examines the significance of digital technologies not only from the standpoint of technological progress but also their role in modernizing processes, particularly within the customs risk management system [17].

The use of AI in organizing temporary storage warehousing includes optimizing goods placement, automatic demand forecasting, planning loading/unloading routes, automatic inventory management, and anomaly detection, which enhances efficiency and reduces costs.

M. Gutium examines the key aspects of implementing artificial intelligence and big data in customs operations management. The author analyzes ways to improve

the conceptual framework of intelligent customs management aimed at enhancing the qualitative efficiency of operations conducted by customs authorities and, ultimately, at modernizing global trade facilitation systems [18].

In order to solve the problem of optimizing the loading/unloading process in the warehouse and logistic distribution, the authors proposed an improved Q-learning algorithm integrating a gravitational potential field and dynamic experience replay. The use of a hierarchical decision-making structure not only increases the performance of the multi-AGV collaborative Q-learning method by approximately 25% compared to independent AGV learning but also reduces the number of mutual deadlocks by approximately 40% [19].

According to M. Elkoutour et al., the application of blockchain technology in customs clearance offers a range of advantages, such as streamlining customs procedures, improving global supply chain management, preventing customs risks, and enabling real-time verification of product quantity, quality, and origin. The use of blockchain technology in this study highlights the potential for increasing the efficiency, transparency, and reliability of international commercial transactions, which can contribute to improved trade conditions and economic growth [20].

Y. Yin et al. developed a semantic enhancement module that integrates a semantic encoder into the rule representation learning process, effectively improving the model's semantic understanding of unstructured customs texts and overcoming the limitations of traditional text processing methods. The research confirms the effectiveness of the SEKD-RRL framework in the task of customs risk rule generation, provides a technical pathway for creating a new generation of intelligent customs risk regulation systems, and serves as a reference for research in areas such as semantically-enhanced rule learning and knowledge-based intelligent decision-making [21].

M. Krzan et al. presented a prototype modification of an existing customs declaration preparation system using Optical Character Recognition (OCR) technology and an Artificial Intelligence (AI) system [22].

Y. E. Gupanova and G. I. Goremykina map the problem of measuring customs authorities' performance in key areas within the context of the qualitative systemic transformation of the customs institution, driven by its intellectualization in the digital economy. The computer implementation of the mathematical models was performed on the MatLab software platform using the Fuzzy Logic Toolbox package [23].

N. H. Karim et al. propose a conceptual model of a “smart warehouse”, termed “futuristic warehouse synergy”, encompassing both internal and external warehouse blockchain. The proposed solution facilitates the creation of a unified online platform allowing shippers and warehouse operators to participate in online booking of warehouse space and cargo storage [24].

The refinement of customs operations involves the implementation of electronic declarations, automation of checks, the use of information systems for cargo tracking, the application of risk management, and the acceleration of clearance procedures, all of which enhance the speed and efficiency of customs processing during temporary storage.

D. Naehar et al. apply a dynamic algorithm to assess the evolution of the global landscape of customs unions, using data on bilateral trade flows of 200 countries from 1958 to 2018. According to the researchers, there is significant variation between different rounds of European Union accession regarding the degree to which they align with the structure of “natural markets”, with some accession rounds following commercial logic more closely than others [25].

A. Shtrikov et al. examine the criteria and principles for evaluating the performance of customs authorities and the quality of customs services, taking into account the specifics of their provision [26].

V. S. Arsenteva et al. pay special attention to pre-arrival notifications for reducing the time allocated for customs operations when importing goods into the customs territory of the EAEU. The authors emphasize the need to hold interested parties accountable for failure to submit or untimely submission of pre-arrival notifications to the customs authority [27].

C. Han et al. conduct a comprehensive investigation and analysis of the declaration process for cross-border road freight. The scholars propose a solution for creating an intelligent customs clearance information system that enables the automation and intellectualization of customs clearance operations [28].

I. Meidutė-Kavaliauskienė and R. Činčikaitė examine the impact of logistics companies' cooperation with third-party logistics (3PL) providers by analyzing opportunities for improving customs processes [29].

M. Z. Karbekova et al. assess the possibilities of supporting businesses striving for greening through the application of customs regulation measures [30].

A number of studies reflect the specifics of customs operations in various countries, which are determined by multiple factors, including legislative norms, infrastructure development levels, customs procedures, documentation requirements, and technological capabilities. In particular, issues of customs regulation are considered using the example of African countries [31; 32; 33], Mexico [34], Jordan [35; 36; 37], Russia [38], and Kazakhstan [39].

Thus, publications by various authors cover a wide spectrum of aspects of customs activity. Authors examine the criteria for evaluating the performance of customs authorities and the quality of services, taking into account their specifics, and investigate the impact of cooperation between logistics companies and 3PL providers on improving customs processes.

Research and developments in the implementation of artificial intelligence, big data, and blockchain technologies in managing customs and logistics operations demonstrate significant potential for enhancing the efficiency, transparency, and automation of these processes. Developed algorithms, such as improved Q-learning, semantic modules, and OCR systems, enable the optimization of logistics, acceleration of customs clearance, improvement of risk management, and enhancement of the overall system quality. The implementation of such innovations contributes to the modernization of customs procedures, strengthens trust among participants in foreign economic activity, and supports the development of the digital economy at the international level.

RESULTS

Goods and means of transport crossing the customs border of the Eurasian Economic Union (hereinafter, EAEU) are subject to placement in a temporary storage warehouse (hereinafter, TSW) or another place of temporary storage (at a customs authority's TSW, in the premises/warehouse/open area/other territory of the consignee, etc.) during the execution of customs operations related to placing goods under temporary storage.

The movement of goods and means of transport across the customs border is performed by various modes of transport: water, rail, air, and road. Furthermore, the practice of transporting goods using two or more modes of transport, i.e., within the framework of multimodal transportation, is common. This requires compliance with the conditions for performing multimodal transportation, which consist of three elements:

- transportation (carriage) of goods by two or more modes of transport;
- a multimodal transport operator (carrier);
- a multimodal bill of lading (transport document).

In order to organize multimodal transportation, the places where goods and means of transport are moved must be equipped with modern facilities and meet all conditions permitting the storage of various categories of goods in specially designated areas. This refers to the organization of special facilities – hub transport and logistics centers (hereinafter, “hubs”).

The arrangement and equipping of modern storage locations must meet advanced standards for the provision of logistics and warehousing services, with goods delivered there by various modes of transport. In this regard, the development of proposals within a roadmap (action plan) for creating new types of TSWs is promising.

The description of a prospective TSW model or another place of temporary storage should also establish requirements for customs control zones within which the storage of goods arriving by various modes of transport and the conduct of forms of customs control, as well as measures to ensure such control, are intended to take place.

The criteria for arranging and organizing a prospective TSW model include the following requirements:

- availability of access roads;
- availability of specially equipped premises and territories for conducting customs control of goods and means of transport, and which allow for the performance of customs operations at any time of the year without causing damage to the goods and means of transport subject to control;
- availability of technical control means, an automatic system for maintaining visual control (a system for reading and recognizing) distinctive marks on goods and means of transport, as well as for detecting illegal actions in the adjacent territory;
- availability of loading and unloading equipment, an automatic system for weight control of goods in containers (during their placement and removal from the territory of “hubs”);

- availability of container yards where loading and unloading of containers onto rolling stock of various modes of transport, sorting of transit containers, selection (sub-grouping) of containers by type of rolling stock, and technical maintenance and repair of containers are carried out;
- availability of an automated goods accounting system compatible with software products approved for use by customs authorities;
- availability of a sufficient number of staff to perform customs operations;
- availability of an internal operational management system for the activities of “hubs”, etc.

The formation of a prospective TSW model or another place of temporary storage should begin with creating suitable facilities in terms of functional capabilities and corresponding to regulatory requirements at the locations for customs and other types of control related to the organization of logistics nodes. Furthermore, existing warehouses should be reoriented as much as possible towards the needs of organizing transport and logistics centers with expanded capabilities for storing, sorting, and issuing goods intended for sale (introduction into circulation) on the domestic market.

Furthermore, the process of digitalizing customs authorities' operations continues. One of the mandatory methods for facilitating and simplifying customs control is the electronic interaction of departmental agencies. In turn, the implementation of digital functions by the customs service and other state departments aligns with the expectations of TSW owners and related intermediaries (distributors, etc.).

The restructuring of supply chains, the growth of online trade, and the rapid pace of change in logistics networks require an acceleration of customs processing and cargo transshipment procedures, as well as an improvement in the quality and economic efficiency of these processes.

According to a forecast for the size, share, and growth rate of the temporary storage facilities/warehouse sheds market for the period 2025–2032, the global temporary storage facilities/warehouse sheds market size is projected to be USD 4.7 billion in 2025 and reach USD 7.7 billion by 2032, growing at a rate of 7.3% each year [40].

Market growth is driven by several key factors. Firstly, significant growth in e-commerce activity creates an increased need for flexible storage solutions capable of scaling quickly in line with changing market demands. Secondly,

industrialization in developing countries creates a necessity for rapid deployment of storage infrastructure, which requires the application of fast-assembly methods and modular construction. Thirdly, there is active adoption of modular construction methods, which can reduce the implementation timeline for new facilities by 30–50% compared to traditional construction approaches. Additional acceleration of market dynamics is provided by increasing infrastructure development costs and the popularization of cost-effective, mobile structures, which contribute to improved efficiency and flexibility of storage systems.

It is also forecast that the temporary storage facilities market will grow from USD 3.1 million in 2025 to USD 5.6 million by 2035, with a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 6.1%. Storage buildings will dominate the market with a 50.6% share, and industrial sheds will lead the structures segment with a 40.4% share [41].

The temporary storage facilities market exhibits diverse regional dynamics, with growth leaders being the USA (6.1% per year) and Brazil (5.7% per year), which are expanding due to investments in e-commerce infrastructure and increased capacity for agricultural storage. India (5.5% per year) is among the emerging markets, benefiting from the development of industrial corridors and logistics infrastructure programs. Established leaders include the United Kingdom (4.6% per year), China (4.4% per year), and Germany (3.9% per year), supported by their developed industrial sectors and flexible capacity needs. Japan (4.6% per year) is considered a mature market, where space constraints and preparedness for natural disasters contribute to steady growth rates.

Table 1

Market dynamics of temporary storage facilities

Country	Compound annual growth rate (2025-2035)
United States	6.1%
Brazil	5.7%
India	5.5%
United Kingdom	4.6%
China	4.4%
Germany	3.9%
Japan	4.6%

Regional analysis indicates that North American markets lead in adopting new technologies due to the expansion of e-commerce services and the acceleration

of infrastructure project implementation. Meanwhile, developing economies demonstrate steady growth supported by industrial development and agricultural modernization trends. European markets show stable growth driven by logistics optimization and construction site efficiency requirements.

The specifics of the temporary storage facilities market in the Asia-Pacific region will be analyzed separately. According to Mordor Intelligence, the self-storage warehousing market in the Asia-Pacific region was estimated at 32.88 million square feet in 2025 and is projected to grow from 35.3 million square feet in 2026 to 50.35 million square feet by 2031, exhibiting a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 7.36% during the forecast period (2026-2031) [42].

The combination of developed and developing economies in the Asia-Pacific region has led to the development of diverse market strategies and infrastructure solutions. In key trading hubs such as Singapore and Hong Kong, digital customs clearance systems and integrated port-warehouse ecosystems are successfully implemented, enhancing the efficiency of logistics operations. In Southeast Asian countries, there is an expansion of logistics capacities and the adoption of inventory management models through supplier collaboration, allowing for more effective handling of seasonal trade peaks. At the regional level, investments are being made in the development of cold chain (temperature-controlled) logistics and systems for managing high-value goods to ensure timely delivery and product quality preservation, underscoring the growing strategic role of customs warehouses as key assets in modern logistics.

The Asia-Pacific region is one of the most dynamically developing markets in the construction of temporary storage structures and warehouse sheds. The region is characterized by significant growth in production and consumption, with China holding a dominant position both in terms of production capacity and consumption structure. India, in turn, is becoming a strategic direction for the expansion of international companies due to its high growth potential. Rapid industrialization in China and the increase in e-commerce volumes are stimulating significant demand for flexible warehouse infrastructure, which is supported by state policies focused on urbanization and manufacturing development. The region benefits from competitive labor costs, developed supply chains, and extensive experience in producing steel and modular structures. The Indian warehousing sector demonstrates particular dynamism, with a high rate of new warehouse space absorption expected in the coming years. Countries of the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN), including Vietnam, Indonesia, and Thailand, are

experiencing steady production growth, creating an imminent need for solutions to store raw materials and finished products. A young demographic structure, rising disposable income levels, and the development of digital technologies contribute to the sustained growth in demand for retail and logistics infrastructure. These factors create favorable conditions for the deployment of temporary storage structures across various sectors and industries in the region.

According to Grand View Horizon, the revenue from storage services in the Asia-Pacific region is projected to reach an estimated USD 18,172.0 million by 2030 [43].

Intense urbanization, the growth of e-commerce, and changing lifestyles are significantly altering the demand for storage space. Concurrently, the existing fragmented property base, comprising 1,495 facilities, creates opportunities for their consolidation and optimization. Parallely, investor interest in this market segment is increasing, driven by the reevaluation of traditional real estate segments and the growing popularity of alternative assets. In an environment of high and stable long-term interest rates, the self-storage warehousing market in the region is viewed as a reliable income source. Operator companies utilizing technology, multi-story formats, and neighborhood placement strategies gain a competitive advantage through improved occupancy rates. Facilities located in areas with fire safety and building code restrictions that complicate the construction of new warehouse complexes benefit particularly. These factors contribute to the formation of a stable and dynamically developing industry that meets the requirements of the modern market and long-term growth prospects.

When selecting a distribution center in the Asian region, numerous factors must be considered, with their importance varying depending on the specifics of the particular business. The presented diagram (see Fig. 1) illustrates a hypothetical rating system for evaluating different cities based on six key criteria.

The choice of specific cities for analysis depends on the company's set goals and requirements. Popular distribution center locations in Asia traditionally include cities such as Taipei, Hong Kong, Shanghai, Shenzhen, and Singapore, as well as port cities located in Malaysia, Thailand, Vietnam, Indonesia, and India.

DISCUSSION

The obtained data confirm the significance of factors influencing the development of the self-storage warehousing market in the Asia-Pacific region. In particular, a

high degree of urbanization and population growth have a determining impact on demand. Forecasts by the Asian Development Bank indicate further expansion of urban centers, which will necessitate finding efficient storage solutions for both personal and business purposes. The growth of the urban population, especially in megacities such as Shanghai, Tokyo, and Mumbai, leads to a reduction in available residential space and increased development density, making new storage formats essential to provide adequate space with limited resources. An additional factor is the rising income of the middle class in the region's countries, which stimulates consumer demand and expands the need for diverse storage options. An important market driver is the exponential growth of e-commerce, which increases the demand for flexible and rapid logistics solutions. Overall, the research results emphasize that self-storage facilities, which also function as micro-fulfillment centers, provide cost-effective and scalable solutions that meet the requirements of the modern dynamic market.

Assessment Tool for Warehouse Hub Selection				
Criteria	City	City	City	City
Service Levels Proximity to suppliers / customers and related delivery speed	●	●	●	●
Taxes & Duties Costs to import / export	●	●	●	●
Regulatory Environment Ease of doing business, including regulations, financing, incentives	●	●	●	●
Transport Infrastructure Country road infrastructure as well as freight capacity and connection to global gateways	●	●	●	●
Productivity Adjusted Labor Costs Labor availability and cost	●	●	●	●
Total Landed Costs Analysis of all factors and the impact on total cost	●	●	●	●
Overall Suitability				

Figure 1 Evaluation tools for warehouse center selection [44]

Based on the research results, it can be concluded that the initiative to develop the organizational and technological aspects of temporary storage warehousing appears promising and capable of enhancing the region's global competitiveness by improving the efficiency of international logistics chains and reducing costs. In the future, the expanded application of automated warehouses, increased international cooperation, and the implementation of innovative cargo tracking and security technologies are anticipated.

CONCLUSION

The warehousing industry is undergoing a significant transformation phase. The implementation of innovative solutions, such as process automation, environmentally-oriented technologies, and e-commerce support, enables companies to enhance operational efficiency, increase profitability, and improve customer satisfaction levels.

These trends are corroborated by current data, including key warehousing operation statistics and industry analytical indicators, which provide a basis for making informed and strategically sound decisions. Optimizing warehouse process efficiency unlocks their potential and helps align with modern global standards and trends.

Shifts in the geography of goods distribution and structural changes in retail are generating a sustained empirical demand for the creation of high-performance TSWs. For instance, in online trade, a major portion of sales (in China, Southeast Asia, the USA) is concentrated on large marketplaces hosting millions of resellers and brand suppliers offering products. This increases the flow of consolidated cargo and the overall order volume, which require rapid and high-quality consolidation when crossing state borders.

The development of global trade, global supply chains, the expansion of sales geography for global suppliers, and price competition amidst generally weakening demand necessitate extremely efficient transportation and customs processing of goods, as well as convenient and rapid consolidation of shipment batches and cargo handling at the warehouse.

These changes reflect the growing relevance of constructing and developing TSWs, whose infrastructure will expand amidst shifting geography of export-import operations and increasing cargo flows along new international transport corridors.

REFERENCES

1. Rui, K., & Feng, L. (2025). Bonded Warehouse. In: *Yinxing, H. (eds) Dictionary of Contemporary Chinese Economics*. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-97-4036-9_349
2. Hoyano, F., & Ishigaki, A. (2026). Efficiency Classification of Picking Methods in Warehouses Using Dynamic Programming Considering Temporary Storage and Picker Capacity Constraints. In: *Mizuyama, H., Morinaga, E., Nonaka, T., Kaihara, T., von Cieminski, G., Romero, D. (eds) Advances in Production Management Systems. Cyber-Physical-Human Production Systems: Human-AI Collaboration and Beyond. APMS 2025. IFIP Advances in Information and Communication Technology, vol 765*. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-032-03534-9_27
3. Albert, P. W., Rönnqvist, M., & Lehoux, N. (2023). Trends and new practical applications for warehouse allocation and layout design: a literature review. *SN Applied Sciences, 5*, 378. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42452-023-05608-0>
4. Sinha, A. K., & Muralidhar, P. (2024). Application of Lean Technique in Warehouse Operations for Waste Reduction. In: *Kashyap, A., Raghavan, N., Singh, I., Renganaidu, V., Chandramohan, A. (eds) Sustainable Lean Construction . ILCC 2022. Lecture Notes in Civil Engineering, vol 383*. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-99-5455-1_8
5. Hu, X., & Chuang, Y. F. (2023). E-commerce warehouse layout optimization: systematic layout planning using a genetic algorithm. *Electronic Commerce Research, 23*, 97–114. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10660-021-09521-9>
6. Ayad, M., & Siadat, A. (2022). Approach for Optimisation Warehouse Storage Areas Based on the Container Storage Problem. In: *Hamlich, M., Bellatreche, L., Siadat, A., Ventura, S. (eds) Smart Applications and Data Analysis. SADASC 2022. Communications in Computer and Information Science, vol 1677*. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-20490-6_22
7. Hsu, W. K., Ngoc Le, T. N., & Huynh, N. T. et al. (2025). Relocation policy for container terminals in a seaport: a gap index approach using hybrid DEMATEL-fuzzy AHP. *Journal of Marine Science and Technology, 30*, 677–692. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00773-025-01074-y>
8. Berković, M., Nikšić, L., & Šimić, E. (2025). Cargo Terminals: A Comparative Analysis of European Airports and Sarajevo Airport. In: *Karabegović, I., Kovačević, A., Mandžuka, S. (eds) New Technologies, Development and Application VIII. NT 2025. Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems, vol 1483*. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-95197-8_25
9. Zhao, Y., Kim, T., & Hwang, B. S. (2025). Improving customs clearance bottleneck in the Chinese B2C import cross-border e-commerce: extending sampling methods by two stages. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications, 12*, 1001. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-025-05261-5>
10. Bandaranayake, N., Kiridena, S., & Kulatunga, A. K. et al. (2024). Analysing cross-border logistics operations for performance improvement: development and validation of a reference model. *Operations Management Research, 17*, 1531–1552. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12063-024-00519-8>
11. Moshkina, N. A., Kondrashchenko, D. A., Bekher, V. V., Gelyahova, L. A., & Mashekuasheva, M. H. (2023). Improving Control Activities and International Cooperation of Customs Authorities in the Context of Digitalization. In: *Buchaev, Y. G., Abdulkadyrov, A. S., Ragulina, J. V., Khachatryan, A. A., Popkova, E. G. (eds) Challenges of the Modern Economy. Advances in Science, Technology & Innovation*. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-29364-1_75
12. Mamyrova, S., Alibayeva, G., & Adilova, K. et al. (2025). Comparative analysis of digital technologies and legal frameworks in customs operations: A focus on violation detection. *Journal of Transportation Security, 18*, 27. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12198-025-00316-9>
13. Valetskyi, B., Zaleta, O., Povstianoi, O., Redko, R., & Zaleta, A. (2026). Automation of Warehouse Parameters Calculation and Its Sketch Design. In: *Tonkonogyi, V., Ivanov, V., Luściński, S., Trojanowska, J., Oborskyi, G. (eds) Advanced Manufacturing Processes VII. Interpartner 2025. Lecture Notes in Mechanical Engineering*. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-032-14926-8_7
14. Pan, Y., Zhang, X., Zhang, F., Tan, L., Yang, L., & Ma, J. (2024). Design Technology of Multi-AGV Warehouse Intelligent Scheduling Optimization Control System. In: *Lin, J. CW., Shieh, CS., Horng, MF., Chu, SC. (eds) Genetic and Evolutionary Computing. ICGEC 2023. Lecture Notes in Electrical Engineering, vol 1145*. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-97-0068-4_45

15. Chen, Y., & Jiang, Z. (2024). Multi-AGVs Scheduling with Vehicle Conflict Consideration in Ship Outfitting Items Warehouse. *Journal of Shanghai Jiaotong University (Science)*, 29, 492–508. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12204-022-2561-z>
16. Prokudin, G., Chupaylenko, O., Khabotnia, T., Hilevska, K., & Prokudina, I. (2024). Simulation of Truck Customs Terminal Work. In: Prentkovskis, O., Yatskiv (Jackiva), I., Skačkauskas, P., Karpenko, M., Stosiak, M. (eds) *TRANSBALTICA XIV: Transportation Science and Technology. TRANSBALTICA 2023. Lecture Notes in Intelligent Transportation and Infrastructure*. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-52652-7_42
17. Seturidze, R. (2024). Enhancing Economic Growth Through Digital Technologies: A Focus on Customs Risk. In: Geibel, R. C., Machavariani, S. (eds) *Digital Management to Shape the Future. ISPC 2023. Springer Proceedings in Business and Economics*. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-66517-2_6
18. Gutium, M. (2025). Digital Transformation of Customs Management: The Use of Artificial Intelligence and Big Data to Improve the Efficiency of Customs Service. In: Xu, J., Dabo-Niang, S., Binti Ismail, N. A., Gao, N. (eds) *The Nineteenth International Conference on Management Science and Engineering Management. ICMSEM 2025. Lecture Notes on Data Engineering and Communications Technologies*, vol 264. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-95-1595-0_50
19. Wang, F. X. et al. (2025). Research on the Joint Optimization Algorithm of Q-learning Plane Warehouse Pickup and Logistics Distribution. In: Huang, D.S., Pan, Y., Chen, W., Li, B. (eds) *Advanced Intelligent Computing Technology and Applications. ICIC 2025. Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, vol 15854. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-96-9901-8_38
20. Elkoutour, M., Raji, H., & Bakhat, M. (2024). Blockchain Technology and Customs Clearance Procedures: Facilitating and Smoothing Products Importation in Morocco's Customs and Excises Administration. In: Azrour, M., Mabrouki, J., Guezzaz, A. (eds) *Sustainable and Green Technologies for Water and Environmental Management. World Sustainability Series*. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-52419-6_6
21. Yin, Y., Shi, S., Huang, H., Qiao, C., & Li, Y. (2025). Semantic-Knowledge Infused Rule Representation Learning for Enhanced Customs Risk Rule Generation. In: Huang, D. S., Chen, W., Pan, Y., Chen, H. (eds) *Advanced Intelligent Computing Technology and Applications. ICIC 2025. Communications in Computer and Information Science*, vol 2575. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-95-0017-8_9
22. Krzan, M., Dudycz, H., & Suchomski, M. (2025). Artificial Intelligence in the Automation Process of Customs Declaration Preparation: A Case Study of an International Logistics Company. In: Hernes, M., Wątróbski, J., Roś, A. (eds) *Emerging Challenges in Intelligent Management Information Systems. ECAI 2024. Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems*, vol 1217. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-78465-1_4
23. Gupanova, Y. E., & Goremykina, G. I. (2023). Measurement of Customs Performance in Conditions of Customs Institute Intellectualization. In: Makarenko, E. N., Vovchenko, N. G., Tishchenko, E. N. (eds) *Technological Trends in the AI Economy. Smart Innovation, Systems and Technologies*, vol 625. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-19-7411-3_30
24. Karim, N. H., Md Hanafiah, R., Abdul Rahman, N. S. F., & Abdul Hamid, S. (2022). Introduction of Futuristic Warehouse Synergy: A Warehouse Storage Space Reservation Hub System. In: Ismail, A., Dahalan, W. M., Öchsner, A. (eds) *Advanced Maritime Technologies and Applications. Advanced Structured Materials*, vol 166. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-89992-9_23
25. Naeher, D., De Lombaerde, P., & Saber, T. (2025). Evaluating accession decisions in customs unions: a dynamic machine learning approach. *International Economics and Economic Policy*, 22, 2. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10368-024-00632-w>
26. Shtrikov, A., Persteneva, N., & Shtrikova, D. (2023). Assessment of the Quality of Customs Services. In: Guda, A. (eds) *Networked Control Systems for Connected and Automated Vehicles. NN 2022. Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems*, vol 510. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-11051-1_136
27. Arsenteva, V. S., Arkhipova, M. V., Yakushevskaya, E. A., Gorbunova, V. B., & Levit, E. A. (2023). Automation of Customs Operations as an Element of Creating a Single Point of Acceptance

- of Extended Advance Notification About the Importation of Goods into the Customs Territory of the Eurasian Economic Union at Air Border Crossing Points. In: Bogoviz, A. V. (eds) *Big Data in Information Society and Digital Economy. Studies in Big Data*, vol 124. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-29489-1_31
28. Han, C., Wang, B., & Lai, X. (2024). Research on the Construction of Intelligent Customs Clearance Information System for Cross-Border Road Cargo Between Guangdong and Hong Kong. In: Zhao, F., Miao, D. (eds) *AI-generated Content. AIGC 2023. Communications in Computer and Information Science*, vol 1946. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-99-7587-7_15
 29. Meidutė-Kavaliauskienė, I., & Činčikaitė, R. (2023). Optimization of Customs Processes for Improving Cooperation Between Third-Party Logistics Companies. In: Prentkovskis, O., Yatskiv (Jackiva), I., Skačkauskas, P., Maruschak, P., Karpenko, M. (eds) *TRANSBALTICA XIII: Transportation Science and Technology. TRANSBALTICA 2022. Lecture Notes in Intelligent Transportation and Infrastructure*. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-25863-3_50
 30. Karbekova, M. Z., Grabar, A. A., Soboleva, O. N., Sukhinin, A. V., & Kotandzhyan, A. V. (2023). Customs Regulation in Support of Development of Climate-Responsible Entrepreneurship in Digital Economy Markets. In: Popkova, E. G. (eds) *Smart Green Innovations in Industry 4.0. Springer Climate*. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-45830-9_12
 31. Ngoben, B. M. (2025). The Causes and Effects of Poor Customs Administration on the Successful Implementation of the African Continental Free Trade Area Agreement (AfCFTA): The Need to Digitalise Customs Procedures in Africa. In: Warikandwa, T. V., Chitimira, H., Osode, P. C. (eds) *Law and Policy of the African Continental Free Trade Area (AfCFTA). European Yearbook of International Economic Law()*. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-032-01122-0_11
 32. Rachidi, L., & Touhami, L. (2022). The Integration of the Customs Clearance Single Window in the Development of Customs-Business Partnerships in Morocco. In: Kacprzyk, J., Balas, V. E., Ezziyyani, M. (eds) *Advanced Intelligent Systems for Sustainable Development (AI2SD'2020). AI2SD 2020. Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing*, vol 1417. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-90633-7_90
 33. Dere, I. G., Ojekunle, J. A., & Sanni, L. M. (2025). Analysis of the effects of berth characteristics on operational performance of Nigerian seaports. *Journal of Shipping and Trade*, 10, 26. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41072-025-00216-0>
 34. Reyes, O., & Pérez, O. (2025). The Green Customs Initiative (GCI) and the Multi-lateral Environmental Agreements (MEAs): An Analysis of the Perception about its Implementation and Compliance in Customs Manzanillo, Colima, Mexico. In: Ivanova Boncheva, A., Rangel Delgado, J. E. (eds) *Transition to a Safe Anthropocene in the Asia-Pacific. The Anthropocene: Politik—Economics—Society—Science*, vol 39. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-66521-9_16
 35. Barhoom, F. N. I. et al. (2025). Continuous Improvement: Exploring the Relationship Between Six Sigma Implementation and Organizational Agility in the Jordan Customs Department. In: Al-Sartawi, A., Ghura, H. (eds) *Artificial Intelligence, Sustainable Technologies, and Business Innovation: Opportunities and Challenges of Digital Transformation. Studies in Computational Intelligence*, vol 1171. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-77925-1_71
 36. Al-Zaqeba, M. A. et al. (2026). The Effect of Implementing AI-Driven Customs Processes on Trade Facilitation Efficiency in Jordan. In: Alshehadeh, A. R., El-Qirem, I. A., Elrefae, G. A. (eds) *Artificial Intelligence in Business. SICB 2025. Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems*, vol 1502. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-96622-4_11
 37. Alkhwaldah, R. (2025). AI-integrated procurement and inventory systems in Jordanian customs points and employee performance: evidence from e-commerce supply chains. *Future Business Journal*, 11, 252. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s43093-025-00661-0>
 38. Maksimov, S. A. (2025). Transport and Logistics Infrastructure of the Novosibirsk Hub as a Basis for Interaction with China and Central Asian Countries. *Regional Research of Russia*, 15, 482–491. <https://doi.org/10.1134/S2079970525600532>
 39. Assilbekova, I., & Konakbay, Z. (2026). The Business Model of an Automated Warehouse with the Integration of the Cargo World Application. In: Karakoc, T. H., Abdullayev, K., Dalkiran, A., Mirzayev, F., Aghayev, E., Cinoğlu, B. (eds) *Research and Updates on the Use of Artificial*

Intelligence in Drone Technology. ISUDEF 2024. Sustainable Aviation. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-032-07678-6_71

40. Zope, R. (2025). *Temporary Storage Buildings/Sheds Market Size, Share, and Growth Forecast 2025 - 2032 - Persistence Market Research.* Persistence Market Research. <https://www.persistencemarketresearch.com/market-research/temporary-storage-buildings-sheds-market.asp>
41. Kaitwade, N. (2025). *Temporary Storage Building Market/Temporary Storage Building Market Forecast and Outlook (2025-2035).* Future Market Insights. Available at: <https://www.futuremarketinsights.com/reports/temporary-storage-buildings-market>
42. *Asia-Pacific Self Storage Market | 2021 - 26 | Industry Share, Size, Growth - Mordor Intelligence.* (n.d.). www.mordorintelligence.com. <https://www.mordorintelligence.com/industry-reports/asia-pacific-self-storage-market>
43. *Asia Pacific Self-Storage Market Size & Outlook, 2030.* (2026). [Grandviewresearch.com](http://www.grandviewresearch.com). <https://www.grandviewresearch.com/horizon/outlook/self-storage-market/asia-pacific>
44. Dimerco. (2023). *Strategic Warehousing in Asia-Pac.* Dimerco. <https://dimerco.com/ebooks/strategic-warehousing-in-asia-pac/>

INFORMATION ABOUT THE AUTHORS

Nazira A. Gumar	Cand. Sci. (Economics), Associate Professor. Almaty Technological University. Almaty, Republic of Kazakhstan. E-mail: gumnaz@mail.ru . ORCID ID: 0000-0001-7516-899X. Scopus Author ID: 56027794000. ResearcherID: AEL-5969-2022	Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing - Original Draft, Visualization
Asan A. Satmurzaev	Professor, Dr. Sci. (Econ.), Professor of the Graduate School of Finance and Accounting. Turan University. Almaty, Republic of Kazakhstan. E-mail: ncasan@mail.ru . ORCID ID: 0000-0002-5208-6761	Investigation, Writing - Review & Editing

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist

Copyright: © Nazira A. Gumar, Asan A. Satmurzaev, 2026

Editor: Vinicius Martinez. Université Paris Cité (France)